

CERTIFICATE

◆◆◆ THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO ◆◆◆

O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Narzullaev Shodiyor Eshpulatovich

UTILIZING THE OPPORTUNITIES OF BUSINESS INCUBATORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT

OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI

2023/IYUN

